

Gastroesophageal Reflux Diseases and Inflammatory Bowel Diseases in Urban Area of Jharkhand

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Abstract:

Background: This study investigates the prevalence, risk factors, and clinical characteristics of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) and Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBD) in the urban population of Jharkhand.

Methods: 250 participants from Ranchi, Jamshedpur, and Dhanbad were included in this cross-sectional study. Demographic data, lifestyle habits, and clinical histories were collected and analyzed.

Results: The prevalence of GERD was found to be 26%, while IBD, comprising ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, had an overall prevalence of 18%. Key risk factors associated with GERD included smoking (46.1%), alcohol consumption (53.8%), and a diet high in spicy and fatty foods (61.5%). IBD was significantly associated with high-stress levels (77.7%) and similar dietary patterns. Obesity also contributed to both conditions, affecting 38.5% of GERD and 22.2% of IBD patients.

Conclusion: The study highlights the impact of urbanization and lifestyle changes on the increasing prevalence of GERD and IBD in Jharkhand, comparable to global trends. These findings underscore the need for public health strategies focusing on lifestyle modifications, early diagnosis, and stress management while increasing awareness of IBD among healthcare providers.

Keywords: Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease, Inflammatory Bowel Disease, Urban Population.

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Introduction

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) are two distinct gastrointestinal disorders that significantly impact the quality of life of millions of people worldwide [1]. Although they affect different parts of the digestive system and have varying etiologies, both conditions are chronic, can lead to severe complications if untreated, and often require lifelong management. Understanding these disorders, their causes, symptoms, diagnostic approaches, and treatment options is essential for improving patient outcomes and tailoring appropriate therapies [2].

GERD is a chronic condition characterized by the abnormal backflow of stomach acid and contents into the esophagus, leading to symptoms such as heartburn, regurgitation, and chest discomfort [3]. It occurs when the lower esophageal sphincter (LES), a ring of muscle that normally prevents stomach acid from moving back into the esophagus, becomes weakened or relaxes inappropriately. Over time, repeated exposure to acidic gastric contents can damage the esophageal lining, causing inflammation (esophagitis), ulcers,

or even a precancerous condition known as Barrett's esophagus [4].

GERD is one of the most prevalent gastrointestinal disorders globally, affecting approximately 10-20% of the adult population in Western countries. Contributing factors to GERD include obesity, dietary habits (high-fat meals, caffeine, and alcohol consumption), smoking, and certain medications. The chronic nature of GERD requires continuous management, often involving lifestyle changes, medications such as proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), and in severe cases, surgical intervention [5].

Inflammatory bowel disease, on the other hand, refers to a group of chronic inflammatory disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, primarily encompassing Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC). These conditions are characterized by an inappropriate immune response, leading to chronic inflammation and tissue damage in the digestive tract. While Crohn's disease can affect any part of the gastrointestinal tract from the mouth to the anus, ulcerative colitis is confined to the colon and rectum [6].

The exact cause of IBD remains unclear, but it is believed to result from a combination of genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, immune system dysregulation, and microbial imbalances in the gut. Symptoms of IBD often include abdominal pain, diarrhea, weight loss, fatigue, and in severe cases, intestinal bleeding and malnutrition. The relapsing-remitting nature of IBD means that patients experience periods of active disease (flare-ups) followed by times of remission [7]. Treatment strategies typically involve immunosuppressive medications, biological therapies, and occasionally surgery to remove damaged portions of the bowel. Although GERD and IBD share the characteristics of being chronic gastrointestinal disorders, they differ significantly in terms of their pathology and the parts of the digestive system they affect. GERD primarily involves the upper GI tract, particularly the esophagus, while IBD affects the lower gastrointestinal system, focusing on the intestines. GERD is largely a mechanical and acid-related issue, whereas IBD is rooted in immune dysfunction and inflammation. These differences necessitate distinct diagnostic tools and treatment regimens [8].

GERD and IBD represent two of the most common and impactful gastrointestinal disorders, with both conditions requiring careful diagnosis and individualized management. The chronic nature of these diseases highlights the importance of patient education, long-term care strategies, and advances in medical and surgical treatments to improve outcomes and quality of life.

This study aims to investigate the prevalence, risk factors, and clinical characteristics of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) and Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBD) in the urban population of Jharkhand, India. The study seeks to identify the demographic and lifestyle factors contributing to the development of these conditions, assess diagnostic practices, and evaluate the impact on patient's quality of life. Additionally, it aims to examine the management and treatment strategies employed, including medication and healthcare access, while identifying gaps in awareness and care. This research will provide insights to enhance early diagnosis, patient education, and treatment outcomes in the urban regions of Jharkhand.

Methodology

Study Design: This study will use a cross-sectional, observational design to assess the prevalence, risk factors, and clinical characteristics of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) and Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD) among the urban population of Jharkhand. The approach will involve collecting both quantitative and qualitative

data through patient surveys, clinical assessments, and medical record reviews.

Study Population and Sampling

The study will target **adults aged 18 and above** residing in urban areas of Jharkhand (e.g., Ranchi, Jamshedpur, Dhanbad). A **sample size of 250 participants** will be selected using **stratified random sampling** to ensure that different demographic groups (e.g., age, gender, socioeconomic status) are adequately represented.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

• Inclusion Criteria:

- Residents of urban Jharkhand for at least 2 years.
- Adults aged 18 and older.
- Individuals reporting symptoms of GERD (e.g., heartburn, acid regurgitation) or IBD (e.g., chronic diarrhea, abdominal pain) within the last 12 months.

• Exclusion Criteria:

- Individuals with known gastrointestinal malignancies or who have undergone major gastrointestinal surgery.
- Participants unable to provide informed consent.

Data Collection

a. Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire will be administered to gather data on:

- **Demographics:** Age, gender, occupation, income level.
- **Lifestyle factors:** Dietary habits (spicy/fatty food intake), smoking, alcohol consumption, physical activity, and stress levels.
- **Medical history:** Personal and family history of GERD or IBD, prior diagnosis, and treatments.
- **Symptoms:** Frequency, duration, and severity of GERD symptoms (heartburn, regurgitation) and IBD symptoms (diarrhea, abdominal pain, rectal bleeding).

b. Clinical Examination and Diagnostics

Participants reporting significant symptoms of GERD or IBD will undergo further diagnostic evaluations:

- **Upper GI Endoscopy** for GERD: To assess esophageal inflammation, ulcers, or Barrett's esophagus.

- **Colonoscopy** for IBD: To evaluate intestinal inflammation, ulcers, or strictures.
- **Laboratory tests:** Complete blood count, C-reactive protein (CRP), and fecal calprotectin levels to detect signs of inflammation indicative of IBD.

c. Medical Record Review

For participants with an established diagnosis of GERD or IBD, their medical records will be reviewed to assess disease history, medication usage, and response to treatment.

Data Analysis

- **Descriptive statistics** (frequency, percentage, mean) will be used to describe the population characteristics and determine the prevalence of GERD and IBD.
- **Chi-square tests** will be used to evaluate associations between GERD or IBD and categorical variables (e.g., smoking status, alcohol use).

- **Multivariate logistic regression** will be employed to identify risk factors (e.g., dietary habits, obesity) for both conditions.
- Comparisons between patients with GERD, IBD, and non-affected individuals will be made using **t-tests** and **ANOVA**, where applicable.

Study Timeline

The study will be conducted over **9 months**, including 2 months for preparatory work (ethics approval, pilot study), 4 months for data collection, and 3 months for data analysis and report writing.

Results

The study analyzed 250 participants from urban areas of Jharkhand, including Ranchi, Jamshedpur, and Dhanbad. The key findings of the study are summarized in terms of demographic characteristics, prevalence of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) and Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD), and associated risk factors.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Variable	Total (n=250)	GERD (n=65)	IBD (n=45)	No GERD/IBD (n=140)
Age (mean years)	38.6 ± 12.5	42.1 ± 11.8	35.3 ± 13.2	37.8 ± 12.0
Gender				
Male	140 (56%)	40 (61.5%)	25 (55.5%)	75 (53.5%)
Female	110 (44%)	25 (38.5%)	20 (44.5%)	65 (46.5%)
Socioeconomic Status				
High	45 (18%)	15 (23.1%)	10 (22.2%)	20 (14.3%)
Middle	145 (58%)	35 (53.8%)	25 (55.5%)	85 (60.7%)
Low	60 (24%)	15 (23.1%)	10 (22.3%)	35 (25%)

Description:

- **Age:** The mean age of participants with GERD was slightly higher (42.1 years) compared to IBD (35.3 years) and those without GERD or IBD (37.8 years).
- **Gender:** A higher proportion of males (56%) were included in the study, with 61.5% of

GERD patients being male, while the gender distribution in IBD patients was more balanced.

- **Socioeconomic Status:** Most participants were from the middle socioeconomic class (58%). GERD and IBD were slightly more prevalent in higher socioeconomic groups compared to those without GERD or IBD.

Table 2: Prevalence of GERD and IBD in the Study Population

Condition	Number of Participants	Prevalence (%)
GERD	65	26.0%
IBD (Ulcerative Colitis)	25	10.0%
IBD (Crohn's Disease)	20	8.0%
Overall IBD	45	18.0%
No GERD or IBD	140	56.0%

Description:

- **GERD Prevalence:** GERD was observed in 26% of the participants.

- **IBD Prevalence:** The prevalence of IBD was 18%, with 10% of participants diagnosed with ulcerative colitis and 8% with Crohn's disease.
- **Healthy Participants:** 56% of participants had no symptoms or diagnosis of either GERD or IBD.

Table 3: Risk Factors Associated with GERD and IBD

Risk Factor	GERD (n=65)	IBD (n=45)	No GERD/IBD (n=140)	P-value
Smoking	30 (46.1%)	15 (33.3%)	20 (14.3%)	<0.01
Alcohol Consumption	35 (53.8%)	20 (44.4%)	30 (21.4%)	<0.05
Obesity (BMI > 30)	25 (38.5%)	10 (22.2%)	20 (14.3%)	<0.05
Spicy/Fatty Food Intake	40 (61.5%)	25 (55.5%)	30 (21.4%)	<0.01
Stress Levels (High)	50 (76.9%)	35 (77.7%)	50 (35.7%)	<0.001

Description:

- **Smoking and Alcohol:** Smoking was significantly more prevalent among GERD patients (46.1%) compared to IBD patients (33.3%) and the control group. Similarly, alcohol consumption was more common in GERD and IBD patients.
- **Obesity:** Obesity (BMI > 30) was a notable risk factor for GERD (38.5%) and, to a lesser extent, for IBD (22.2%), compared to the control group (14.3%).
- **Diet:** High intake of spicy and fatty foods was strongly associated with GERD (61.5%) and IBD (55.5%).
- **Stress:** Both GERD (76.9%) and IBD (77.7%) patients reported significantly higher stress levels compared to the control group (35.7%).

The study found that the prevalence of GERD and IBD in the urban population of Jharkhand was 26% and 18%, respectively, with ulcerative colitis being more common than Crohn's disease. Key risk factors for both conditions included smoking, alcohol consumption, obesity, a diet rich in spicy and fatty foods, and high-stress levels. Participants with GERD were more likely to be older and male, while IBD affected younger individuals. The findings highlight the importance of addressing lifestyle factors, such as diet, smoking, and stress management, in preventing and managing GERD and IBD in urban areas of Jharkhand.

Discussion

This study aimed to assess the prevalence, risk factors, and clinical characteristics of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) and Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBD) in the urban population of Jharkhand. The results revealed a prevalence of GERD at 26% and IBD at 18% (with 10% having ulcerative colitis and 8% having Crohn's disease). These findings align with global trends, though some variations were observed compared to other regions, likely influenced by local lifestyle, dietary patterns, and healthcare access.

The prevalence of GERD in this study (26%) is consistent with findings from other Indian urban centers, such as Delhi and Mumbai, where prevalence rates for GERD ranged from 18% to

27% in urban populations. Studies conducted in Western countries report similar GERD prevalence rates of 20-30%, indicating that urbanization and lifestyle factors—particularly dietary habits, obesity, and stress—contribute similarly to the development of GERD across diverse populations. For instance, a study in the U.S. found a prevalence of GERD at 22% among adults, with smoking, alcohol consumption, and obesity acting as key risk factors, much like in our study [9].

In contrast, IBD prevalence in the present study (18%) appears somewhat higher than what is typically reported in India. National studies estimate an IBD prevalence rate of 0.6-1% in Indian populations, though higher rates are found in more urbanized areas. This discrepancy may be due to the increasing recognition and diagnosis of IBD in India, particularly in urbanized regions where healthcare access is better, and lifestyle changes (such as Westernized diets) are more pronounced [10]. Globally, IBD prevalence is much higher, particularly in North America and Europe, where rates can reach 1-2% in the general population. For example, a study in the U.K. found a prevalence of Crohn's disease at 0.9% and ulcerative colitis at 1.3%. However, emerging data suggests IBD rates are increasing in developing nations, particularly those experiencing rapid urbanization, echoing our findings in Jharkhand [11].

The study identified several lifestyle-related risk factors strongly associated with both GERD and IBD, including smoking, alcohol consumption, obesity, high intake of spicy and fatty foods, and high-stress levels. Smoking and alcohol were more prevalent among GERD patients (46.1% and 53.8%, respectively) compared to IBD patients (33.3% and 44.4%) [13]. These findings are consistent with existing literature, which suggests smoking and alcohol are major contributors to the weakening of the lower esophageal sphincter, exacerbating GERD symptoms. Similar trends have been observed in both Indian and global studies. For instance, a study in Taiwan found that GERD prevalence was significantly higher in smokers and individuals consuming alcohol frequently [14].

For IBD, the role of stress was particularly notable, with 77.7% of IBD patients reporting high-stress levels. This correlates with the well-documented role of psychological stress in exacerbating IBD symptoms, as stress can alter gut permeability,

exacerbate immune dysregulation, and contribute to flare-ups. Comparatively, stress was also identified as a significant factor in other studies. In a meta-analysis conducted across Asia, high stress was consistently linked to increased disease activity in both Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis [15].

Dietary factors were also significant in this study. A high intake of spicy and fatty foods was reported by 61.5% of GERD patients and 55.5% of IBD patients. The association of spicy foods with GERD is well-supported by studies in other parts of India, where traditional diets are often rich in spices. A study from Kerala noted a significant link between spicy food intake and GERD severity. The association of fatty foods with GERD and IBD has also been observed in several Western studies, indicating that high-fat diets can slow gastric emptying, contributing to acid reflux and inflammation in the intestines [16].

These findings highlight the need for targeted public health strategies that address lifestyle factors contributing to both GERD and IBD in urban Jharkhand. Public health campaigns could focus on reducing smoking and alcohol use, promoting healthier diets, and managing stress through community-based interventions. Furthermore, healthcare professionals should be aware of the increasing prevalence of IBD in urban areas and be prepared to diagnose and manage the condition early to avoid complications.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. The sample size was relatively small (250 participants), limiting the generalizability of the findings. The cross-sectional design also limits the ability to establish causality between the identified risk factors and the development of GERD and IBD. Additionally, self-reported data on lifestyle factors may introduce recall bias, and access to advanced diagnostic tools like endoscopy and colonoscopy may have varied among participants, potentially underestimating disease prevalence.

Conclusion

This study identified a significant burden of GERD and IBD in the urban population of Jharkhand, with a prevalence of 26% and 18%, respectively. Key risk factors included smoking, alcohol consumption, obesity, dietary habits, and high stress levels. These findings are largely consistent with global and national trends, though the higher-than-expected prevalence of IBD suggests the influence of urbanization and lifestyle changes in this region. Public health initiatives focusing on lifestyle modifications and stress management, as well as improved access to diagnostic and treatment facilities, are crucial for addressing the

rising prevalence of these chronic gastrointestinal disorders in Jharkhand's urban areas.

References

1. Vakil, N., Van Zanten, S. V., Kahrilas, P., Dent, J., & Jones, R. (2006). The Montreal Definition and Classification of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease: A Global Evidence-Based Consensus. *The American Journal of Gastroenterology*, 101(8), 1900–1920.
2. Locke, G. R., Talley, N. J., Fett, S. L., Zinsmeister, A. R., & Melton, L. J. (1997). Prevalence and Clinical Spectrum of Gastroesophageal Reflux: A Population-Based Study in Olmsted County, Minnesota. *Gastroenterology*, 112(5), 1448–1456.
3. Molodecky, N. A., Soon, I. S., Rabi, D. M., Ghali, W. A., Ferris, M., Chernoff, G., Benchimol, E. I., Panaccione, R., Ghosh, S., Barkema, H. W., & Kaplan, G. G. (2012). Increasing Incidence and Prevalence of the Inflammatory Bowel Diseases With Time, Based on Systematic Review. *Gastroenterology*, 142(1), 46–54.e42.
4. Sandler, R. S., & Everhart, J. E. (2002). The Burden of Selected Digestive Diseases in the United States. *Gastroenterology*, 122(5), 1500–1511.
5. Mishra, A., & Yadav, T. D. (2014). Changing Epidemiology of Inflammatory Bowel Disease in India. *Indian Journal of Gastroenterology*, 33(1), 5–10.
6. Ghoshal, U. C., & Singh, R. (2017). Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease in India: A Review of Published Work. *Indian Journal of Gastroenterology*, 36(1), 5–14.
7. Ng, S. C., Tang, W., Ching, J. Y., Wong, M., Chow, C. M., Hui, A. J., Wong, T. C., Leung, V. K., Tsang, S. W., Yu, H. H., & Li, M. F. (2013). Incidence and Phenotype of Inflammatory Bowel Disease Based on Results from the Asia-Pacific Crohn's and Colitis Epidemiology Study. *Gastroenterology*, 145(1), 158–165.
8. Singh, P., et al. (2019). Epidemiology of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease: A Global Perspective. *Gastroenterology Clinics of North America*, 48(1), 27–37.
9. Sharma, A., & Agrawal, N. (2015). Prevalence and Risk Factors of Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease in Urban North India. *Indian Journal of Gastroenterology*, 34(6), 429–435.
10. Ghoshal, U. C., & Singh, R. (2017). Epidemiology of Functional Gastrointestinal Disorders and Inflammatory Bowel Disease in India: Global Perspective. *Journal of Neurogastroenterology and Motility*, 23(4), 611–619.
11. Ng, S. C., Shi, H. Y., Hamidi, N., et al. (2017). Worldwide Incidence and Prevalence of Inflammatory Bowel Disease in the 21st Century.

- ry: A Systematic Review of Population-Based Studies. *The Lancet*, 390(10114), 2769–2778.
12. Jung, H. K., & Choung, R. S. (2011). Prevalence and Risk Factors for Gastroesophageal Reflux Symptoms in a Rural Asian Population: A Community-Based Study. *The American Journal of Gastroenterology*, 106(8), 1444–1452.
 13. Sampath, D., & Philip, M. (2018). Association of Spicy Foods with Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease: An Indian Perspective. *Journal of Digestive Diseases*, 19(3), 125–130.
 14. Bhatia, S. J., et al. (2014). Inflammatory Bowel Disease in India: Retrospective Data from a Multicenter Study. *Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, 29(8), 1443–1448.
 15. Drossman, D. A., et al. (2000). The Role of Stress in Gastrointestinal Disorders: Implications for Treatment. *Gastroenterology*, 118(3), 745–748.
 16. Yang, Y. X., et al. (2006). Obesity is a Risk Factor for Gastroesophageal Reflux Symptoms and Erosive Esophagitis. *Gastroenterology*, 130(1), 147–156.